

Analysis of Six Sigma in the Aerospace Industry

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Abstract : This paper subsidizes to the discussion of Six Sigma in the Aerospace Industry. The main aim of this report is to study the literature review of Six Sigma emphasizing on the aerospace industry. The implementation of Six Sigma stages are studied and how the improvement cycle 'Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, and Control cycle' (DMAIC) and the design process is 'Define, Measure, Analyze, Design, and Verify Cycle' (DMADV) is used. The focus is also done by studying how the implementation of Six Sigma on an aerospace company has brought a positive effect to the company.

Keywords : six sigma, DMAIC, DMADV, aerospace

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